

BEHAVIOUR OF SANDWICH BEAMS WITH CONVENTIONAL AND MODIFIED CORE JUNCTIONS UNDER FATIGUE LOADING CONDITIONS

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SUMMARY: The paper considers local effects occurring near junctions between different cores in sandwich structures. Two groups of sandwich beams, with conventional “butt” and reinforced “butt” core junctions, respectively, were manufactured and examined experimentally. The reinforcement of the “butt” junctions was achieved via a local introduction of small reinforcing patches of resin or adhesive agent in grooves machined along the core junctions. The technology of producing such reinforcements with the purpose of faster redistribution of the resin/adhesive is well known, but being applied locally at the junctions, it effectively suppresses local stress concentrations. The sandwich beams with the conventional and modified core junctions were tested in three-point bending under static and fatigue loadings. A rigorous statistical treatment of the obtained data has unambiguously shown that sandwich beams with reinforced “butt” junctions display superior structural performance compared with sandwich beams with traditional core junctions.

KEYWORDS: core junctions, local effects, stress concentrations, design.

INTRODUCTION

A sandwich element composed of two thin, stiff and strong faces separated by a thick and light core represents a lightweight structural component with very high resistance to external bending and transverse loads, substantial strength and considerable buckling limit. Sandwich panels, plates and shells have gained widespread acceptance within the aerospace, marine, automotive, building and sustainable energy industries where they are well accepted due to their excellent structural performance and easy maintenance. Despite the many advantages of sandwich structures, a number of unsolved problems still exist. For practical as well as structural reasons, design of sandwich structures often involves the use of cores of different densities in the form of backing plates, inserts, edge stiffeners, etc. [1-3] within the same structural sandwich element. An abrupt change of the geometry and different elastic properties of the adjoined core materials causes the inducement of local stresses in the core as well as in the faces, and this may jeopardize the structural integrity of the whole sandwich assembly, especially under fatigue loading conditions.

A conventional core “butt” junction [4] presents a straight interface between two adjoining cores, see Fig. 1, where the interface plane terminates with an angle of 90° relative to the sandwich faces. A closed-form analytical model [5] has shown that severe stress concentrations are induced in all constituents of sandwich plates in the near vicinity of core

junctions subjected to transverse loading. Experimental and numerical investigations [6-7] confirmed that these stress concentrations display themselves as an increase of the core principal stresses and a local increase of the bending stresses in the faces near the three-material corners (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Constitution of the experimentally investigated sandwich beams with (a) the face laminate layout (stacking sequence) and (b) a zoom on the two junction types

Sandwich beams subjected to static and fatigue bending loading conditions were experimentally studied in [8-9], with special emphasis on the influence of the shape of the core junction on the fatigue performance. The idea of adopting a structurally graded core junction concept, introduced in [10], implies a structural/design optimisation of a conventional junction (i.e. the interface/boundary between two cores) with the purpose of reducing/diminishing the local stress concentrations near the junction. The conceptual idea of using structurally graded core junctions was substantiated in [8-9], in which geometrically modified core junctions were shown to be structurally superior to conventional core “butt” junctions.

An alternative method of suppressing local effects is to use local reinforcements of the faces in the near vicinity of core junctions [10], see Fig. 1. The introduction of reinforcing patches (see Fig. 1) appears to be a fast, inexpensive and technologically simple method of improving the structural performance and quality of core junctions. Accordingly, the purpose of the work presented here is to demonstrate the benefit of such a design modification through an experimental investigation of sandwich beams with conventional and modified core junctions subjected to the static and fatigue bending loads.

SPECIMENS AND EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The geometry, layout and general loading scheme of the test specimens are shown in Fig. 1, and the elastic properties of the beam constituents are shown in Table 1. The sandwich beam specimens are assembled from two composite laminated faces with a symmetrical lay-up of $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$, and two types of PVC foam cores. All the components of the panel are joined using an epoxy resin, Araldite® 2022 (Huntsman Adv. Materials), with the help of a vacuum bagging technique.

The face laminates (Fig.1 (a)) were made of carbon fibre prepregs (SP Systems [11]), and were manufactured by means of a manual lay-up with subsequent vacuum bagging at the prescribed temperature and pressure [12]. The tensile stiffness of the composite laminates was measured experimentally by means of modal analysis [13] and standard tensile tests [14]. Both methods yielded the same equivalent modulus of elasticity for the laminate face equal to 83.3 GPa with an error of measurement that did not exceed 4%. The mechanical properties of a single lamina appear in Table 1 according to [11].

Table 1: Properties of the sandwich beam constituents

	Faces: Carbon fibre laminate	Compliant core: H60	Stiff core: H200
Modulus of elasticity, MPa	83300	60	310
Shear modulus, MPa	-	22	90
Strength/yield stress, MPa	1190 _{compression-along fibres}	0.8 _{compression}	4.5 _{compression}
	2840 _{tension-along fibres}	1.4 _{tension}	4.8 _{tension}
	12 _{across fibre}		
Shear yield strength, MPa	-	0.7	3.3

Two types of core materials were used in the investigated sandwich beams: a compliant core, H-60, and a stiff core, H-200 (Divinycell from DIAB Group [15]) with densities 60 kg/m³ and 200 kg/m³, respectively. The compliant core was used in the central part of the specimens, and the stiff core was used at the beam ends. The latter prevented indentation of the sandwich structure at the edge supports.

Two groups of sandwich beams, each containing 7 specimens, were manufactured. The first group included beams with conventional “butt” junctions, and the second group included beams with reinforced “butt” junctions as shown in Fig. 1(b). The reinforcing patches were achieved by the machining of circular segment grooves across the junctions, and subsequently filling these grooves with adhesive (Araldite[®] 2022), while attaching the faces to the core. This is a simple technological operation, which is routinely used in the production of sandwich panels in order to enhance the distribution of resin and bonding agent. It should be noted that the geometry of the segment-like reinforcing patch shown in Fig. 1(b) has been substantiated with the help of Finite Element Analysis with the purpose of effectively suppressing the local bending of the faces at core junctions [8-9].

A three-point bending scheme, as shown in Fig. 2, was chosen for the experimental investigation of the sandwich beams [16]. In the chosen loading scheme, both transverse shear force and bending moment loadings are present. However, the peak local effects at the core junctions are due to the transverse loading [5]. The test-rig was mounted in a servo hydraulic test machine, SCHENK Hydropuls[®] PSB [17], and provided with a computerized data acquisition system. The test-rig was operated in displacement control mode, with an accuracy of the load measurements better than 0.2%. Video recording of the experiments with a resolution of 25 frames per second was also enabled.

Fig. 2: Experimental set-up for the three-point bending of sandwich beams with a zoom on the central diaphragm

It is important to mention here that sandwich structures are generally prone to several different failure modes depending on the geometric and elastic properties of the constituents, as well as on the imposed loading and boundary conditions [18-19]. Accordingly, it was extremely important to eliminate undesired failure modes, and to conduct the experiment in such a way that the smallest critical load, which would trigger the failure of the sandwich beam, would correspond to yield/fracture of the compliant core at the core junction. Reference is made to [8] for details of the critical load estimates for the various types of failures, as well as for design considerations concerning the sandwich specimens used for the three-point bending tests.

In addition, the issue of the central loading point and prevention of indentation of the compliant core in the centre of the specimen was solved with the help of a rigid central diaphragm as shown in Fig. 2. The diaphragm with a thickness of 4 mm, was manufactured in a separate mould step from the same adhesive (epoxy), which was used for bonding the sandwich components, and subsequently it was bonded into a rectangular groove machined in the centre of the core material prior to attaching the second face.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From each group of specimens, two sandwich beams were subjected to quasi-static loading and 5 were subjected to cyclic loading until failure occurred.

The quasi-static loading was applied at a loading rate of 0.05 mm/s . The obtained load vs. central displacement diagrams for the sandwich specimens with conventional and reinforced “butt” junctions are presented in Fig. 3. These load-displacement curves are linear up to approximately 1.5 kN , which corresponds to a central deflection of about 5 mm (cf. with the

total thickness of the sandwich beams being 27 mm). The static failure loads are considered as the maximum loads achieved in the testing, and for the specimens with both types of junctions they lie in the rather narrow interval of $2.36\text{--}2.42\text{ kN}$. These strength values are very close (though slightly larger) to a simple estimate of the critical load based on the shear strength of the compliant core from the Table 1: $\tau^Y \cdot area = 2 \cdot 0.7 \cdot 59 \cdot 25 = 2.1\text{ kN}$. It is worth to notice in Fig. 3 that the sandwich beams with modified junctions allow at least 10% larger final deflection than the beams with conventional junctions.

Fig. 3: Load vs. central displacement curves for sandwich beams with conventional and reinforced “butt” junctions subjected to the quasi-static three-point bending loading

Video recordings of the specimens subjected to quasi-static loading allowed the acquisition of some information about the initiation of fracture, see Fig. 4. The consecutive video frames shown in Fig. 4 are separated by a time interval of $1/25$ sec. A 45° -shadow in frame 2 appearing in the soft core, suggests that it is the compliant core, which failed first in the sandwich beams with both conventional and modified/reinforced junctions. The visual evidence of Fig. 4 is not enough to draw an unambiguous conclusion about where exactly in the compliant core that a crack (fracture) initiated before it propagated, either along directions perpendicular to the principle tensile core stresses and/or into a delamination mode of the face-core interfaces. However, the fact that the majority of the sandwich beams subjected to quasi-static or fatigue loadings neither suffered delamination of the face-core interfaces at the beam edges nor in the central loading point area, effectively ruled out all other possibilities than a shear yield of the compliant core. Fracture or crack propagation may as well have started at the three-material corners, and it should be noticed how the shadows in frames 2 are tied to the three-material corners.

Fig. 4: Crack initiation and final rupture in sandwich beams with conventional and reinforced “butt” junctions subjected to quasi-static loading. The time interval between the consecutive video frames 1, 2 and 3 equals 1/25 sec

Fig.5: Characteristic crack patterns in sandwich beams with conventional and reinforced “butt” junctions subjected to quasi-static and fatigue loading conditions

It was chosen to subject both sandwich specimens groups to cyclic fatigue loading of the same level, which was selected to be approximately 70% of the static critical load, i.e. 1.75 kN. A loading ratio of $R=0.1$ provided a fixture of the specimens during testing, and a loading frequency of 3 Hz was used (see Table 2). The testing was conducted using load-

amplitude control. The application of displacement shut-limit control guaranteed that the fracture propagation in the ruptured specimens was stopped before the occurrence of total collapse of the specimens.

Table 2: Fatigue test loading parameters

Static failure load, kN	Fatigue load amplitude, kN	R-ratio	Frequency, Hz
2.36-2.42	1.75	0.1	3

The typical crack patterns are shown in Fig. 5, from which it is observed that they are generally identical for quasi-static and fatigue loadings except for a delamination path near the reinforcing patch. Notice that the rupture runs along the sandwich face when the beams were fatigued, and around the epoxy patch when loaded statically.

Fig.6: Fatigue life of sandwich beams with conventional and reinforced “butt” junctions. The loading parameters are specified in Table 2

The number of cycles to failure was measured for the 5 sandwich beams with conventional “butt” junctions and for the 5 sandwich beams with reinforced “butt” junctions. The results are shown schematically in Fig. 6. Fatigue life times in the interval [19671-57675 cycles] were obtained for the sandwich beams with conventional junctions, whereas fatigue life times obtained for the sandwich beams with reinforced “butt” junctions were in the interval [78535-146023 cycles]. It should be noticed that, in spite of the scatter of the experimental data observed for both specimen groups, the minimum life time of sandwich beams with reinforced junctions was substantially longer than the maximum life time of sandwich beams with conventional junctions. A rigorous statistical treatment of the obtained data was performed to obtain the average value of the fatigue life of each group of sandwich specimens. From the analysis of the test data it was established that the sandwich beams with conventional core junctions displayed a significantly lower mean number of cycles (by a factor 3) to failure than the sandwich beams with modified core junctions: 36.422 cycles to failure for conventional joints, and 105.458 cycles to failure for reinforced core joints.

CONCLUSIONS

Sandwich beams with conventional and modified “butt” junctions were tested experimentally in three-point bending. It has been demonstrated that the use of sandwich panels with core junctions furnished with reinforcing patches improves the fatigue life expectancy significantly, compared with sandwich panels with conventional “butt” junctions. For the particular sandwich panel configuration studied herein, the fatigue life was increased by a factor of almost 3.

It should be stressed out that the use of reinforcing patches do not normally change the overall (global) structural performance of a sandwich structure, though the ultimate static compliance of the investigated modified sandwich beam configuration was slightly improved compared with the baseline configuration with conventional core junctions.

Finally, it should be emphasized that the manufacturing of the inner reinforcing patches is a low-cost technological operation, which is already routinely used in the production of sandwich panels (though with the purpose to increase the resin flow and achieve a faster redistribution of this bonding agent). The results presented herein have shown that the placement of such “resin redistribution” grooves along junctions between different core materials will improve the fatigue strength of the sandwich structures considerably.

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